

NEMO: Building the Next Generation Meta Operating System

Enric Pages-Montanera,
Aitor Alcázar-Fernández
ATOS Spain SA
Madrid, Spain
enric.pages@atos.net
aitor.alcazar@atos.net

Theodore Zahariadis,
Terpsichori-Helen
Velivassaki, Charalabos
Skianis
Synelixis Solutions S.A.
Chalkida, Greece
zahariad@synelixis.com
terpsi@synelixis.com
cskianis@synelixis.com

Rosaria Rossini
Research Department
Eclipse Foundation Europe GmbH
Berliner Allee, Darmstadt,
Germany
rosaria.rossini@eclipse-foundation.org

Maria Belesioti
Ioannis P.Chochliouros
R&D Department
Hellenic Telecommunications
Organization (OTE) A.E
Athens, Attica, Greece
mbelesioti@otereseach.gr
ichochoyliouros@otereseach.gr

Nikolaos Drosos, Emmanouil
Bakiris
R&D Dept., Space Hellas S.A.
Athens, Attiki, Greece
drosos@space.gr
ebakiris@space.gr

Prashanth Kumar
R&D Dept., ASM Terni S.p.A.
Terni, Umbria , Italy
Prashanth.pedholla@asmterni.it

Panagiotis Karkazis, Astik
Samal
Maggioli Group SPA,
Santarcangelo di Romagna, Italy
panagiotis.karkazis@maggioli.gr
astik.samal@maggioli.it

Luis M. Contreras
Telefonica I+D
Madrid, Spain
luismiguel.contrerasmurillo@telefonica.com

Alberti del Rio, Javier
Serrano
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
a.delriop@upm.es
jsr@gatv.ssr.upm.es

Dimitrios Skias, Olga Segou
Netcompany-Intrasoft SA
Luxembourg, Luxembourg,
dimitrios.skias@netcompany-intrasoft.com
Olga.SEGOU@netcompany-intrasoft.com

Sonja Wächter
Conti Temic microelectronic
GmbH
Ingolstadt, Germany
sonja.waechter@continental-corporation.com

ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT) is one of the next big concepts to support societal changes and economic growth, being one of the fastest growing ICT segments. A specific challenge is to leverage existing technology strengths to develop solutions that sustain the European industry and values. NEMO (Next Generation Meta-Operating system) establishes itself as the gamechanger of the AIoT-edge-cloud continuum by introducing an open source, modular and cybersecure meta-operating system, leveraging on existing technologies and introducing novel concepts, methods, tools, testing and engagement campaigns.

NEMO will bring intelligence closer to the data and make AI-as-a-Service an integral part of network self-organisation and micro-services execution orchestration. Its widespread penetration and massive acceptance will be achieved via new technology, pre-commercial exploitation components and liaison with open-source communities. By defining a modular and adaptable mOS (meta-OS) architecture together with building blocks and plugins the

project will address current and future technological and business needs.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Artificial Intelligence • Architectures • Data Management Systems

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence of Things, The Cloud-to-Thing continuum: opportunities and challenges, Meta Operating system

1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of the Internet of Things (IoT) [1-2], projected to see significant growth through 2029, signals a paradigm shift in the way digital technology intersects with human life [3-4]. This proliferation of interconnected “things” gives rise to an array of applications, ranging from urban mobility to smart agriculture and energy management [5]. This evolution moves us towards the

advent of the Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT) - an integration of artificial intelligence with our connected world [6]. However, this transformation poses distinct challenges, specifically with regards to the provision of real-time, secure and trusted support from edge cloud systems, coupled with artificial intelligence.

The NEMO platform [7] is designed to “address” these challenges head-on. It acknowledges the need for on-device intelligence to enable AIoT to act as semi-autonomous entities and recognizes that this intelligence should be an integral part of the AIoT meta-Operating System (mOS). By focusing on a transparent IoT-to-Edge-to-Cloud continuum [8-9], NEMO aims to optimize task migration securely, providing timely orchestration of micro-services.

NEMO also recognizes the importance of providing efficient development tools. By offering intent-based DevZeroOps tools and plugin mechanisms, it facilitates faster development and wider deployment of AIoT services. A key part of NEMO’s strategy is to provide an open and modular mOS, ensuring easy deployment to any AIoT device, while maintaining stringent cybersecurity and privacy standards [10].

NEMO goes further in acknowledging the necessity for high penetration of AIoT applications, which necessitates fostering relationships with open-source communities and incentivizing third parties, especially SMEs and AIoT developers, to adopt and use this technology. Capitalising on existing ecosystems, such as GAIA-X [11] and Eclipse IoT [12], NEMO leverages their strengths to enhance its own capabilities, ultimately paving the way towards the AIoT era [13].

Within this paper we provide a comprehensive overview of NEMO mOS Architecture along with a description of i) underlying technologies, ii) NEMO living labs, and iii) NEMO open source community, elaborating on how we aim to work in order to address the aforementioned challenges and contribute to increase the European autonomy in data processing required by future AIoT and hyper-distributed applications [14].

2 Overview of NEMO Concept

Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT) is one of the future big concepts to support social change and economic growth as one of the fastest-growing segments of ICT. A *particular* challenge is using existing technological strengths to develop solutions that help the European industry and its values [15].

In general, fully distributed computing and federation between heterogeneous IoT, edge and cloud nodes introduces cybersecurity concerns [16], as the attack surface is significantly increased. Moreover, there is no standard method to describe a cybersecurity, Intrusion Detection System (IDS), policy or privacy enforcement system, further complicating the provision of end-to-end cybersecurity over an ad-hoc IoT fog/cloud [17]. The most widely applied survivability and self-healing methods [18-19] consider: (a) securing cyber assets; (b) modelling, simulation, and analysis to understand and enable fundamentally robust and fault-tolerant systems, and; (c) systems architecture that can overcome vital limitations. However, the diversity of equipment and protocols

used in the communication and control of IoT and the lack of interoperability create obstacles for anyone attempting to establish secure communications.

To this respect, NEMO establishes itself as the game-changer of the AIoT-edge-cloud continuum by introducing an open source, modular and cybersecure meta-operating system, leveraging on existing technologies and introducing novel concepts, methods, tools, testing and engagement campaigns. NEMO will bring intelligence closer to the data and make AI-as-a-Service [20-21] an integral part of network self-organisation and micro-services execution orchestration. Its widespread penetration and massive acceptance will be achieved via new technology, pre-commercial exploitation components and liaison with open-source communities.

3 NEMO mOS Architecture

NEMO pursues a close collaboration among semi-autonomous IoT nodes, IoT fog clusters, far-edge and near-edge cloud, national and federated cloud infrastructures. Following a **flexible collaboration model**, new generation AIoT nodes will be equipped with intelligence to function in a semi-autonomous mode, reducing the latency and performing a number of complex operations locally, without transporting raw data. Federated on-device learning and data sovereignty and trusted, explicitly attested (edge) cloud nodes will bring AI to environments with limited network coverage. **Local AI models execution (FML, DRL and TL) will result in reduced latency.** This will enable, for example, an industrial wind turbine to be shut down in milliseconds when it recognizes an imminent problem, thereby preventing significant damage and saving expensive downtime; an autonomous car to avoid crashing or injuring a pedestrian, even if network connectivity is temporarily or accidentally lost; or an electricity Grid Supervision Unit to autonomously decide to start or stop an MV transformer when electricity surpass or malicious cyberattack is detected. In parallel, powered by envisioning “free will” based communication, **IoT devices may get support from other IoT nodes in vicinity or a trusted edge cloud node, or the cloud realizing a transparent AIoT- Edge-Cloud continuum.** During off-line training, the federated ML models will be aggregated at an edge node, to be processed and combined through TL. The inter-DLT transactions and the smart contracts will be facilitated by trusted edge nodes, allowing resource constrained nodes to acquire a full “ground truth” using novel approaches, such as “decentralized beacons”. Complex and potentially malicious functions will be executed at the edge nodes using a secure micro-services framework and container-based sandboxing techniques.

Based on the above principles, the core of NEMO will be based on a loosely-coupled set of components, indirectly interfacing open source pipeline management tools (e.g. Apache Airflow) and event-driven backbones (e.g. Apache Kafka or LightweightM2M). As shown in Figure 1, though the lower layers are split between the Smart IoT and the Edge/Cloud Infrastructure, due to the IoT devices constrained environment, in the upper layers there is a “unified” federation that enables transparent execution of vertical semi-autonomous applications and data sharing, governed only by the application’s SLO. In a bottom up approach, NEMO foresees:

Figure 1 NEMO Functional Stack Vision

- Realisation of **transparent network connectivity**, consisting of a set of IoT/5G/6G network optimization functions and dynamic allocation of self-aware resources into self-constructed/self-healing and zero-delay failback network clusters. Aiming to offer ad-hoc/opportunistic clouds and zero delay failback “by design” in the IoT-to-Edge-to- Cloud continuum, instead of a single communication technology, we will introduce a polymorphic **meta Network Cluster Controller (mNCC)** that will be able to interface independent and different tools and protocols and, where it is possible, to replace one technology with another. NEMO will study and validate various options including Eclipse Zenoh.net and ETSI OSM, along with various multi-path connectivity approaches (i.e. MPTCP, CMT- SCTP, AEPS), dynamically constructed via secure FML models and experiment with network zone and path-aware protocol stacks (i.e. QUIC) encapsulating control and/or data plane information. NEMO will also experiment with full micro-services isolation by extending, 5G (micro-)slices into ad-hoc network zones, making it impossible for the application domain to exchange packets outside the network zone (i.e. protecting from external penetration and DDoS attacks), but also (soft) SLO isolation, allowing an application to request guaranteed bandwidth with probabilistic latency properties. To gain accurate information from network resources but still keep flexibility and openness, NEMO will interface existing Monitoring Tools (e.g. CNCF Prometheus, and the highly available setup of Thanos), and Network Management tools (e.g. ETSI MANO) to directly request dedicated resources (i.e. micro-slices with specific bandwidth, delay and encryption characteristics), while FML algorithms will be utilized for enabling advanced multi-path, multitenant connectivity over IoT and 3GPP data flows. NEMO will also leverage on TSN bridge technology and time synchronization aspects to validate service stability, quality and compatibility with IEEE TSN systems.

- The NEMO core functionality will be offered by an AI-based **meta-Orchestrator**, which will automatically, and in real-time, re-configure the mOS setup at each node (either IoT, Edge, Cloud, ad-hoc or hybrid Clouds), so that the end-to-end federation operates optimally, matching the applications’ SLOs and the policies set by the mOS administrators. The meta-Orchestrator will consider a number of existing solutions such as open source containers’ platforms and orchestrators (i.e. Docker, Kubernetes, Minikube, K3S, MicroK8s, Kubermatic or OpenShift), technological,

business and policy priorities, ranging from high availability and low latency to reduced energy consumption and CO2 footprint to cost and community incentives trade-offs and will dynamically (re-)render micro-service and unikernels or even update automatically the hosting clusters. To support the micro- services mesh, NEMO will evaluate and, if needed, extend the CNCF opentelemetry and Linkerd for metering and analyzing software performance, tracking success rates, latencies, and request volumes for every meshed workload, while for micro-services coordination and discovery, solutions such as CoreDNS and etcd will be evaluated. Of significant importance in the decision making will be the **volume and “greenness” of the consumed energy and the CO2 footprint**. In addition, NEMO is supporting securely and transparently migrating VMs between federated Data Centers (DCs), considering not only the required electricity consumption for IT processing and communications, but also the RES mix and required cooling energy (e.g. via water/air flow, geothermal) in Green DCs and the gain of transparent migration between DCs of the same or federated administrative domains.

- NEMO also foresees a novel **Secure Execution Environment (SEE)** implementing operational tasks in close interaction with the micro-services. The framework will be secure “by design”, implemented by using the state of the art and most advanced programming language in security (eg. RUST). A version of the SEE for the edge cloud is already under development in IoT-NGIN project and a version for IoT devices will be implemented within NEMO. It is also worth noticing that recent Zenoh-pico (released in Oct. 2021) is fully implemented in RUST and evaluation shows a significant performance improvement. Moreover, based on containerd, NEMO SEE will manage the complete micro-service life cycle, from image migration and storage to hosting, execution and supervision of both fully trusted/digitally signed micro-services instances along with potentially malicious ones, while updates from external Vulnerability Catalogues will continuous update cybersecure ML models.

- **Federated Data Sovereignty Space**. Though not primary focus of NEMO, special emphasis will be put on supporting at design phase the Data Sovereignty Space. NEMO will follow GAIA-X approach and adopt some of the emerging Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) technologies, such as Hyperledger Indy, including the Sovrin SSI protocol, or the TangleID for IOTA. The cybersecurity of data sharing federation will be based on DLTs. Using the insights from the H2020 projects SOFIE and PHOENIX, NEMO will introduce the novel **Cybersecure Micro-services’ Digital Twins (CMDT)** concept to offer DLT traceability and DT scalability to micro-services instances. Moreover, NEMO Data Space will be open to support technologies for green and responsible data management

- **DevZeroOps Platform as a Service (PaaS)**. NEMO innovates by realizing a DevZeroOps layer offering full- stack automated operations, greatest flexibility, improved developers’ productivity and direct monetization and sustainability. A key component for NEMO success will be a flexible **Plugin & Applications Life-Cycle Manager** that will enable over the air and on-time deployment of required plugins. This will keep NEMO “kernel” size tiny, while enabling cognitive auto-configuration. NEMO will also interface external plugins and microservices catalogues (e.g. GAIA-X, SONATA) to offer a “living” collection of functionalities, published under open source license. This approach

will also allow 3rd parties to select among the components and create new innovative IoT services. Moreover, NEMO will extend Eclipse IDE, with a set of AI-based controllers and their relevant northbound interface, which will offer “**Intent Migration as a Service**”. Towards ZeroOps deployment, this task will fully automate traditional manual processes and deliver configurations towards full-stack automated operations, such as service provisioning, resource configuration, applications life cycle management and automated response to infrastructure issues. Last but not least, MOCA will support pre-commercial exploitation in a multi-user, multi-operator, multi-tenant environment. **MOCA** will use ECL Zenoh APIs and protocols (i.e. DDS, MQTT) for efficient and lightweight implementation, introduce flexible business models and directly interface NEMO meta-Orchestrator to receive information on network micro-slices/ multi-path connectivity, micro-services discovery, migration and execution, policies and SLO requirements.

Beyond horizontal, NEMO will also introduce 3 vertical layers that support all mOS activities. In details:

- NEMO will introduce a **Cybersecure Federated MLOps** layer to offer efficient on-device intelligence in the form of decentralized, cybersecure FML/DRL to be used as integral part of any IoT node decision or (semi-) autonomous operation. NEMO will not only offer on-device MLOps APIs but also research towards cybersecure FML in the form of CF-DRL against cyber-attacks to assist ML-based anomaly detection and implement novel low and medium interaction adversarial nets to identify malicious or suspicious IoT nodes.
- NEMO will enforce **PRESS & Policy compliance** via multi-faced, policies able to cope with the different aspects of the applications life cycle (security, privacy, costs, environmental impact, etc). Multiple relevant paradigms from the cloud-native world will be researched and selectively adapted, e.g. at the level of service mesh to cope with core network utilization/performance, PRESS and native encryption.
- **Cybersecurity & Unified/Federated Access Control Layer**. Beyond “by design” traceability and cybersecurity, NEMO will offer cloud native cybersecurity, interface various authentication and authorization frameworks (e.g. 5G-AKA, EAP-AKA) and adopt the federated ID approach of GAIA-X, along with encryption and identity verification, adapted to the AIoT capabilities.

3.1 NEMO Underlying Technology

NEMO relays on several basic building blocks at infrastructure level providing essential functionality for the secure delivery of services in the cloud-edge continuum.

One of those blocks, named **Cybersecure Micro-services’ Digital Twins (CMDT)**, will assist on the deployment of micro-services by proactively taking into consideration several operational parameters, like e.g. identity, location and owner, memory, CPU, storage, etc., to determine the more convenient deployment. This is expected to be done in a secure manner by utilizing DLT technology as an intrinsic part of the digital twin. The output of the CMDT will help to validate the viability of the service as composition of a number of micor-services deployed in the cloud-edge continuum.

Another relevant block is the **Cybersecure Federated Deep Reinforcement Learning(CF-DRL)**. This module will leverage on federated machine learning techniques to produce optimizations on top o the requested services, so that the usage of resources and the service expectations could be optimized. The module will combine different data sources by privately and securely combining local ML training, in order to update a global model useful for the overall cloud-edge continuum under NEMO.

Moreover, the underlying network substrate interconnecting the continuum will be managed by a **meta Network Cluster Controller (mNCC)**. This module will assist on the establishment of the necessary connectivity end-to-end. On the other hand, the module will expose network capabilities so that can be consumed by other modules in NEMO (related to the underlying technology, but not only) so that the decisions taken for the service delivery can take into account network status and topology.

All these modules cooperate with the rest of the NEMO architecture so that a complete lifecycle of the micro-services can be accomplished in an optimized way, from the fulfilling up to the assurance.

3.2 NEMO Kernel Space

The NEMO Kernel Space is aimed to cover key aspects of a comprehensive framework for secure execution, privacy enforcement, cybersecurity and intelligent orchestration [22] in the context of next-generation AIoT-edge-cloud continuum environments.

The **Micro-services Secure Execution Environment (SEE)** framework aims to facilitate the migration of micro-services, unikernels and binaries by leveraging container and hypervisor technologies. The use of the Rust programming language enhances security and simplifies auditing processes. SEE also offers the option to download unikernel or binary images directly onto IoT devices, reducing software complexity and improving overall efficiency.

Moving forward, the **PRESS, Safety & Policy enforcement framework** addresses various concerns in the next-generation AIoT environment, particularly those related to privacy, data protection, ethics, security and societal implications. The task involves analyzing the impact of personalized sensing on privacy and developing benchmarking criteria to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed framework in limiting information exposure. A policy enforcement framework is designed to ensure compliance with the policies set by service and application providers. Cloud-native paradigms, such as service mesh and the Kubernetes Scheduler Extender, are incorporated to tackle different aspects of the application lifecycle.

The **Cybersecurity & Digital Identity attestation** framework delves into the realm of cybersecurity aspects within the NEMO platform. The task involves analyzing the cybersecurity requirements of NEMO, considering various components such as CMDT, CF-DRL, micro-slices, network zones, and SEE. The focus is on identifying tools and extensions that enable end-to-end secure execution of micro-services, including networking and interconnections security. The adoption of Linux Security Modules strengthens the security measures. Furthermore, the task

emphasizes the importance of Digital Identity attestation and explores protocols like 5G-AKA and EAP-AKA, with a particular emphasis on the federated ID approach of GAIA-X [11].

Finally, the NEMO meta-Orchestrator aims to implement an intelligent orchestrator to streamline decentralized computing

3.3 NEMO DevZeroOps Service Management

NEMO will be introducing a set of enabling tools and mechanisms, namely

Plugin & Applications Life-Cycle Manager that consists a flexible mechanism for unified, just-in-time plugins and applications life cycle management across the NEMO ecosystem. By default, based on applications' requirements/manifest, the NEMO Plugins' & Applications Life-Cycle Manager will gain ingress access rights, download the necessary plugins and associated dependencies on demand, and install them on the devices, totally transparently to the user, while checking for security warnings. Moreover, it will check for available updates/bug fixing and install them over the air. The tool will be based on Jenkins plugins ecosystem.

Monetization and Consensus-based Accountability (MOCA) mechanism as NEMO FinOps component, empowering pre-commercial exploitation of the NEMO ecosystem and ensuring the sustainability. MOCA will enable the creation of new revenue streams' via a "migration marketplace" that will allow volunteers and professionals to adopt the NEMO platform and offer hosting/migration microservices. MOCA will closely collaborate with the meta-Orchestrator and the CMDT to create a distributed, tamper-resistant blockchains- based ledger between different operators and verticals to track provenance and enforce secure negotiation and transaction of resources such as through smart contracts. Moreover, for intersystem messaging solutions such as Crossbar will be analyzed and utilized.

Intent Based Migration for ZeroOps deployment will be realized via a set of AI-based controllers and their relevant northbound interface, which will offer "Intent Migration as a Service". Towards ZeroOps deployment, this task will fully automate traditional manual processes and deliver configurations towards full-stack automated operations, such as service provisioning, resource configuration, applications life cycle management and automated response to infrastructure issues. The intent-based migration component will receive declarative services' migration requests in high level YAML format, interface with the Policy Compliance Framework and automatically convert them to a full E2E cluster configuration, facilitating micro-services and unikernels migration in the IoT/ Edge/Cloud continuum, while guaranteeing the required QoS over a highly dynamic network, compute and storage landscape. As a starting point, we will employ the HELM Kubernetes package manager and extend it with additional CRDs and intelligence components render it capable of properly extracting the business and operational intents out of the provided configurations.

Integration, penetration testing, and Lab V&V will provide the CI/CD/CP infrastructure, which will enable extensive functional and bug fixing on all SW components, Testing, Validation & Verification (V&V) testing, along with penetration testing without interrupting the real Living Labs operations, by utilising the NEMO Integration Infrastructure.

4 Overview of NEMO Living Labs

NEMO pilots will be federated to enable cross-NEMO services deployment and even cross-living labs micro-services mitigation. The federation will be further extended via the Open Calls. Initially, the cross-NEMO agreement mechanism will be exploited to facilitate the interactions between the technology and the living labs. Nonetheless, it is considered of major importance for the envisioned AIoT ecosystem [23] the exploitation of data sovereignty in different locations to be accessed (after anonymization) across different platforms, as well as the federation/aggregation of already trained ML models from similar applications (e.g. drones, autonomous robots) to be used as starting point for the training of new ML models focusing new underlying infrastructures. The NEMO interfaces abstraction will allow apps in one trial to be exploited by applications from a different platform, while data semantics and analytics will facilitate the data exploitation.

4.1 Smart Farming Use Case & Living Lab

This use case will combine multiple types of ground micro-climate/soil/leaf information stations, agri-drones, semiautonomous mobile robots and wearable devices to reduce spraying and support organic olives harvesting.

4.1.1 Use case applications

Aerial Precision Bio-Spraying aims to protect the olive trees from olive fruit fly, while preserving the organic certification, there is a need for frequent spraying of natural mineral ingredients (i.e. Zeolite or Kaolin). We plan to combine micro-clima data and real-time video analysis of the crop from visual and multi-spectral cameras located on semi-autonomous drones flying over the olive trees plantation and identifying in real-time where biospraying is needed. By porting NEMO on SynField and agri-drones, we will validate the execution of real-time CF-DRL based video analysis on the drone based on semi-trained ML models and utilizing Transfer Learning, or at the edge based on FML, applying migration of the video analysis task, and dynamically adjust drones' trajectory to introduce optimal, precision aerial bio-spraying only in areas of interest.

Terrestrial Precision Bio-Spraying. Organic insecticides preserve the bio certification, but require frequent spraying, while in larger quantities increase the cost and may also affect the bees. In NEMO, we plan to use semiautonomous robots equipped with cameras to locate weeds and enable optimal precision spraying with organic insecticide (pyrethrin). Using NEMO CF-DRL, the robots will be able to, while avoiding workers (safety) and trees (operating reasons). In parallel, wearable devices (smart phones) will collect location and activity data workflows across IoT, edge, and cloud

environments, following the Continuum paradigm. The task involves studying existing micro-schedulers and orchestrators, such as Apache Airflow¹ and Netflix Genie², and utilizing CF-DRL intelligence to assess orchestration strategies for containerized micro-services and unikernels. Various factors, such as migration, placement, scaling, and parameters like migration time, downtime, and overhead time, are taken into consideration during the analysis. Additionally, the task includes an examination of factors like network availability, resource utilization, policies, energy efficiency, CO2 footprint, and FinOps requirements, ensuring a comprehensive and holistic approach to orchestrating computing workflows.

4.2 Smart Energy & Smart Mobility/City Use Cases & Living Lab

These Use cases will combine energy data collected from high tech power sensors, smart meters, photovoltaic cell controllers to demonstrate the capability of smart grid asset performance management and optimize the grid operations. And data collected via IoT devices, charging stations, electric vehicles and video analysis of parking cameras to model and train distributed AI models on parking prediction in a greedy layer wise fashion.

4.2.1 Use cases applications

Smart Grid Flexibility: Aims to improve distribution grid operation and the power quality, reducing impact on the grid due to voltage variations caused by reverse power flows. NEMO will investigate advanced AI/ML based analytics to identify potential local energy grid discrepancies and monitor power quality to provide timely alarms when the system is approaching unstable operational boundaries, which could lead to power failures. Also, this would be beneficial for balancing intermittent feed-in from Renewable Energy Sources.

Smart Mobility/City: Aims to improve Renewable Energy Sources (RES) load balancing via EV chargers, predict traffic flow/parking prediction via EV chargers and parking positions for Mobility. Driver-friendly scenarios for smart city mobility and dispatchable charging of EVs based on RES demand-response along with human-centred smart micro-contracts and micro-payments will be realized to deal with new opportunities and new obstacles created by the simultaneous transition to renewable energy and electric mobility.

4.3 Smart Manufacturing & Industry 4.0 Use Cases & Living Lab

The Smart Manufacturing & Industry 4.0 Use Case at Continental aims the Improvement of mass production and safety in factories with high levels of automation.

Fully automated indoor logistics/supply chain: This use case targets ADAS manufacturing. Today, handling and transport of material (SMD-Components) from Auto Store to production sites is performed manually every 30 minutes. By utilizing a 3D-Vision-

Camera for Bin Picking Application, integrated Barcode Scanner and collaboration between different robot systems (one cobot and several types of AGVs), we aim to fully automate controlled material picking from Auto Store and autonomous transfer to the production line.

Human-centred indoor factory environment safety. This use case will provide a high precision AGV localization layer merging real time localizations info obtained from cognitive sensors (safety cameras, radar and lidar). A high speed and ultra-low latency (TSN) private wireless network will support massive data uploads to the edge cloud facilities, where AI functions will detect the position of each body and build a "safety shell" around it to ensure human-centred safety, while federated CF-DRL will enable model transfer learning to the AGVs to enable autonomous avoidance of potential collision between AGVs, or between a worker and an AGV.

4.4 Smart Media/ City & XR Use Cases & Living Lab

Smart Media/ City & XR Use Cases are expected to combine multiple heterogeneous smart wearables, 3D video projectors, advanced AR/VR/XR headsets and low cost devices such as smartphones and tablets.

4.4.1 Use case Applications.

Round of Athens Race: During a round of Athens race, media content will be captured by many spectators along the running circuit using smartphones, a few professional and CCTV cameras. Incoming content will be automatically processed, annotated and rendered (partially on the device using already trained AI/ML models and partially at the edge), and a selection is directly broadcasted (e.g. via social media) based on location info of the (top) runners and interesting events during the race (e.g. based on contributor annotation). The audience will have the option to improve its contributions and will be able to interact with contributors in case of specific race incidents.

XR Time Machine: The scope of this use case is to push the boundaries of immersive experience by optimizing multi-sensorial stimuli via effects such as wind, heat, vibration, in addition to audiovisual (AV) and tactile. An environment that will enable multiple users to interact with virtual or augmented/XR worlds ranging from a virtual trip to a house in Ancient Greece to augment dinosaurs in today's world will be created. In addition a great increase in terms of bandwidth (8K/12K resolutions for 360o video & geometry plus textures for 3D media, optionally accompanied by metadata like lighting, rendering shades, etc.) that also manifests in tighter latency requirements for streaming content, due to the higher refresh rates (90Hz for VR head mounted displays and 240Hz for AR headsets)

5 Open Source Community in NEMO

¹ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

² <https://netflix.github.io/genie/>

NEMO adopts an open source policy and strong liaison with alliances, communities & initiatives. This is the strategy put in place by the consortium to sustain the project results as well as objectives. The strategy starts with the dissemination. The aim of the dissemination is to communicate the results, get to know the project, and build a strong network and interest in the NEMO project. On top of this, NEMO project can start building a community. Once the dissemination and the community building have played their role, the community liaison is the key to start creating the sustainability of the NEMO project.

For this reason, the project is in relationship with several business and development communities. Each of these communities provides us the opportunity to present and be challenged on the different facets of NEMO project. Here are listed the actions in liaison with these communities:

Gaia-X³ is a European private sector initiative for developing an open, federated and interoperable data infrastructure build on top of digital sovereignty. NEMO will target the areas in which the project can contribute with its results.

AIOTI⁴ NEMO use cases will be presented in AIOTI WG 12: Smart Energy, CONTI to WG 11: Smart Manufacturing and SYN to WG 06: Smart Farming, aiming to engage early adopters, find prominent users and develop joint activities.

DAIRO⁵ is the updated version of the BDVA community, now including not only data, but also AI and robotics within its target. There are several ways of contributing to it, NEMO can organize or co-organize a workshop to show results in front of a multidisciplinary audience; or even participate within the BDVA Marketplace to offer tailored solutions for its community.

5GPPP⁶, Partners can heavily leverage the NEMO framework to set the roots for the coming 5G and Smart Networks and Services industrial partnerships as a key enabler of a trustworthy, resilient, sustainable and open next generation IoT.

NEMO will actively collaborate with other 5G PPP and non - 5GPPP projects. The liaisons that will be established, will ensure a successful collaboration and a smoother integration of technologies and concepts.

NGI7 (Next Generation Internet), NEMO is strongly aligned with the NGI core values and intends to collaborate in NGI community activities, such as outreach, event organization and webinars.

Eclipse Working Groups provide a vendor-neutral governance structure that allows organizations to freely collaborate on new technology development. Among all the Eclipse Working group, NEMO identified the Eclipse IoT Working Group⁸ as the most relevant for the topic. In particular, Eclipse IoT Working Group⁸ is an ecosystem of companies and individuals that are working together to establish an Internet of Things based on open technologies. It provides open source implementations of the standards, services and frameworks that enable an Open Internet of Things.

European Cloud, Edge & IoT Continuum Cluster⁹: NEMO has a strong collaboration with the European initiative called European Cloud, Edge & IoT Continuum. In this respect, different Task forces have been created by European Cloud, Edge & IoT Continuum aims to provide strategy and tools to promote the establishment of a European industrial Open ecosystem for continuum computing based on open-source and open standards as well as help project to enhance the sustainability of their results.

5 Summary and Future Work

Within this paper we have outlined the numerous challenges posed by the rapid evolution from Internet of Things (IoT) to the Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT), and how the NEMO platform addresses them. The platform emphasizes the need for on-device intelligence, with the goal of enabling AIoT devices to function as semi-autonomous entities. NEMO works towards creating a seamless IoT-to-Edge-to-Cloud continuum, while ensuring the secure and efficient migration of tasks. This is achieved through the provision of intent based DevZeroOps tools and plugin mechanisms, which facilitate the development and deployment of AIoT services. NEMO also strives to deliver an open, modular mOS, which simplifies deployment to any AIoT device, without compromising on security or privacy. The underlying technologies were presented and architecture layers and components were further detailed.

The overview of NEMO living labs was presented detailing the implementation of each living lab along with the technologies to be applied and the metrics that are going to be used.

Moreover, it was present how the platform will facilitate the adoption of AIoT technology by engaging with open-source communities and incentivizing third-party entities, primarily SMEs and AIoT developers.

Based also on the above-described details, the significant potential of the NEMO platform is clear. However further work could be considered. Future efforts could be focused on refining the mOS, with the objective of enhancing its modularity and ease of deployment. Furthermore, within NEMO we could further optimise its intent based DevZeroOps tools and plugin mechanisms to further streamline the development process and widen the deployment of AIoT services. We will also continue fostering relationships with open-source communities, providing incentives to third-party entities, and leveraging the strengths of existing ecosystems. Most importantly, NEMO is committed to reinforcing its engagement with Living Labs and the open-source community, focusing on real-world applications to enhance the effectiveness of the platform, further address the challenges they are facing and contribute to increasing European autonomy in data processing. In

³ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

⁴ <https://aioti.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.bdva.eu/DAIRO>

⁶ <https://5g-ppp.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.ngi.eu/>

⁸ <http://iot.eclipse.org>

⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

doing so, NEMO will continue to shape the landscape of AIoT and the future of hyper-distributed applications.

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